

The synthesis of Sintenin, a new cytotoxic ester from *Piper sintenense*

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A first short synthesis of Sintenin **1** has been accomplished starting from 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde **2** utilizing Knoevenagel condensation and catalytic hydrogenation using Pd/C as key reactions, in almost quantitative yield. The identity with the naturally occurring compound Sintenin was established on the basis of ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR data.

Piper sintenense HATUSIMA (Piperaceae) is an endemic scandant plant growing in medium altitude forests throughout Taiwan¹. Its leaves and stems have been used as folk medicine against snake bite and wounds². Chen *et al.* investigated the active specie *P. sintenense* and reported the isolation of some new cytotoxic agents against cell lines³. A $\text{CHCl}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1) extract of this specie exhibited cytotoxic activity against P-388, A-549 and HT-29 cell lines *in vitro*. One of the components of this extract Sintenin **1**, an ester, has been assigned the structure **1** on the basis of spectral analysis⁴. A final and rigorous proof of the structure of a natural product is provided through its synthesis, which is being reported for **1** in this communication. The synthesis is not only of academic interest but also a route for bulk production of the cytotoxic ester **1**, which is obtainable from the natural source in trace amount⁴.

Results and discussion

Knoevenagel condensation of 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde **2**, an inexpensive starting material, with malonic acid **3** in pyridine with catalytic amount of piperidine yielded the cinnamic acid **4** in 81% yields⁵. The acid **4** was reduced via catalytic hydrogenation using 10% Pd/C in absolute ethanol to procure the saturated acid **5** in almost quantitative yield⁶. Further reduction of the acid **5** using $\text{NaBH}_4/\text{TiCl}_4$ gave the corresponding saturated alcohol **6** in good yield⁷. Esterification of **5** with **6** in acidic medium gave the title compound **1** in 65% yield. The spectral data of the synthetic sample **1** was found consistent with that reported in the literature⁴.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR were obtained at 300 MHz on Varian FT-

NMR spectrometer using CDCl_3 as solvent. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to TMS. Sodium sulfate was used as the drying agent.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Sintenin.

(*E*)-3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)acrylic acid (**4**): A mixture of 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde **2** (5 g, 30 mmol) and malonic acid **3** (4.7 g, 45 mmol) in dry pyridine (30 mL) and piperidine (1 mL) was heated at 120°C for 6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°C and concentrated HCl (40 ml) was added to pH < 3. The white solid **4** was collected, yield : 5.04 g (81%); m.p. 182–183°C; ν_{max} 1685, 1626, 1597, 1585, 1516, 1427 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR δ 3.76 (3H, s), 3.78 (3H, s), 6.38–6.44 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz), 6.93–6.96 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz), 7.28–7.29 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 7.47–7.52 (1H, d, J 15.9 Hz), 12.1 (1H, s); ^{13}C

NMR 56.2, 56.3, 112.8, 115.2, 115.6, 119.7, 128.5, 148.1, 149.0, 149.7, 170.6.

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)propanoic acid (5) : To a solution of **4** (1 g, 4.8 mmol) in absolute ethanol (150 mL) was added 10% Pd/C, and it was hydrogenated at 30 psi H₂ for 1 h. The reaction mixture was filtered over sintered G-4 glass crucible and the filtrate was concentrated to yield a shiny white solid **5**, yield 1.01 g (100%), m.p. 96–97°C; ν_{\max} 3024, 1701, 1592, 1518, 1432, 1344 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR δ 2.70–2.75 (2H, m), 3.29 (2H, m), 3.68 (3H, s), 3.70 (3H, s), 6.68–6.70 (1H, m), 6.80–6.83 (2H, m), 12.0 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR 33.8, 36.4, 56.2, 56.4, 112.8, 115.2, 121.1, 132.8, 147.0, 149.7, 177.4.

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)propan-1-ol (6) : A solution of **5** (0.8 g, 3.8 mmol) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane (10 mL) was added drop wise to an ice cooled stirred solution of TiCl₄ (0.79 g, 4.18 mmol) and NaBH₄ (0.47 g, 12.5 mmol) in anhydrous 1,2-dimethoxyethane (40 mL). Stirring was continued for 18 h at room temperature and the reaction mixture was then quenched by addition of water (100 mL) with ice cooling. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 40 mL). The organic extracts were washed with brine, dried and evaporated to give **6**, yield 0.5 mL (65.7%); ν_{\max} 3354, 1609, 1589, 1432 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR δ 1.89 (2H, m), 2.60 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz), 3.68 (3H, s), 3.70 (3H, s), 4.1 (2H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz), 6.68–7.70 (1H, m), 6.80–6.83 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR 32.3, 33.6, 56.4, 62.5, 115.4, 121.5, 131.4, 147.1, 149.7, 149.9.

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)propyl-3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)propionate (1) : A mixture of **5** (0.5 g, 2.3 mmol) and **6** (0.58 g, 3.2 mmol) in dry benzene (60 mL) with catalytic amount of pTSA was refluxed for 8 h.

The mixture was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (20 mL). The organic extracts were dried and evaporated to give the final compound **1** as colorless oil, yield 0.65g (73%); ν_{\max} 1730, 1591, 1515, 1454 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR δ 1.92 (2H, m), 2.60 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz), 2.62 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 2.91 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 3.84 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 3.87 (6H, s), 4.10 (2H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz), 6.69 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz), 6.69 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0 Hz), 6.74 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 6.75 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 Hz, 1.5 Hz), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz); ¹³C NMR δ 30.4, 30.6, 31.7, 36.2, 55.8, 55.9, 63.8, 111.6, 120.1, 120.2, 133.1, 133.7, 147.3, 147.5, 148.8, 173.0. EI-MS (70 eV) *m/z* [M⁺] 388, 210, 179, 178, 163, 151, 147, 121, 107, 91.

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